

THE EFFECT OF LEAD SALT ON INTESTINAL CARBOHYDRATE ASSIMILATION IN FISH UNDER *IN VITRO* CONDITIONS

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Annotatsiya: Suvdagi ksenobiotiklar kontsentratsiyasining oshishi natijasida baliqlarning reproduktiv tizimlariga salbiy ta'sir ko'rsatadi. Og'ir metallar baliq tanasida to'planganligi sababli, ular inson tanasiga osongina kirib, salbiy oqibatlariga olib kelishi mumkin. Qo'rg'oshin monoamin oksidaza va atsetilxolin esteraza faolligini pasaytirib, baliqdagi impulslarning o'tkazuvchanligini bloklaydi. Qo'rg'oshin immunitet tizimini zaiflashtiradi va infeksiyalarga moyillikni oshiradi. *in vitro* sharoitida qo'rg'oshin tuzining ($PbNO_3$) 0,4 ml ta'siri ostida laktozaning metabolizmi ichakning 3 ta qismida ham keskin pasaydi. Saxoroza va maltozaga nisbatan deyarli salbiy ta'sir ko'rsatmadi.

Kalit so'zlar: *in vitro*, proksimal, distal, medial, $PbNO_3$, og'ir metallar.

Аннотация: Повышенная концентрация ксенобиотиков в воде оказывает негативное воздействие на репродуктивную систему рыб. Поскольку тяжелые металлы накапливаются в организме рыб, они легко могут попасть в организм человека и вызвать негативные последствия. Свинец блокирует проведение импульсов у рыб, снижая активность моноаминоксидазы и ацетилхолинэстеразы. Свинец ослабляет иммунную систему и повышает восприимчивость к инфекциям. В условиях *in vitro* под влиянием 0,4 мл соли свинца ($PbNO_3$) резко снижался метаболизм лактозы во всех 3 отделах кишечника. Он практически не оказал отрицательного воздействия на сахарозу и мальтозу.

Ключевые слова: *in vitro*, проксимальный, дистальный, медиальный, $PbNO_3$, тяжелые металлы.

Annotation: The increased concentration of xenobiotics in water has a negative effect on the reproductive systems of fish. Since heavy metals accumulate in the body of fish, they can easily enter the human body and cause negative consequences. Lead reduces the activity of monoamine oxidase and acetylcholine esterase, blocking the conduction of impulses in fish. Lead weakens the immune system and increases susceptibility to infections. Under *in vitro* conditions, under the influence of 0.4 ml of lead salt ($PbNO_3$), lactose metabolism decreased sharply in all 3 parts of the intestine. It had almost no negative effect on sucrose and maltose.

Key words: *in vitro*, proximal, distal, medial, $PbNO_3$, heavy metals.

Nowadays, due to the rapid development of industry and the increasing salinity of the soil, the amount of metals in water and soil is increasing. This situation has a direct impact on aquatic organisms, especially fish, and causes a number of negative changes. Heavy metals and their salts accumulate in a number of vital organ systems of fish, namely, muscles, liver, digestive system, kidneys and gills, causing a significant deterioration in the productivity and viability of fish [1]. In particular, lead and its salts affect the physiological processes of fish and cause pathological changes. They weaken the immune system and cause disruption of reproductive organs [2]. Fish are mainly considered as bioindicators for heavy metal pollution in water bodies [3]. The biological activity of heavy metals and their uptake by living organisms depend on various factors, such as their concentration, water temperature, pH, interaction with other metals, fish metabolism, feeding behavior, age and size, and the physicochemical properties of the environment [4].

Fish products are a rich source of protein and fatty acids for humans. Heavy metals accumulate in the fish body and can easily enter the human body and cause adverse effects [5].

Materials and methods

The experiment was carried out on carp fish. The fish were killed between 9 and 10 am in the morning, and the abdominal cavity was opened, and the digestive system was removed. The water bath was filled with ice water, and a glass window was placed on the water bath. This condition ensures the stability of the environment in the digestive system. On the glass window, the digestive system was separated from the fat and intestinal mesentery. Then it was washed with distilled water to remove the chyme in the digestive tract. On the glass window,

the intestine was divided into 3 equal parts, proximal, medial and distal. The length of each intestinal segment was measured, and the intestinal mucosa was removed for dilution. The mucosa of each intestinal segment (proximal, medial, distal) was diluted 10, 50, and 300 times for carbohydrate substrates (lactose, saccharose, and maltose) using distilled water respectively.

Carbohydrates (lactose, saccharose and maltose) were taken as substrates and 2% solutions of each substrate were prepared. Lactose was used as a substrate for 10-fold diluted intestinal sections (proximal, medial, distal), sucrose was used as a substrate for 50-fold diluted intestinal mucosa, and 2% maltose solutions were used as a substrate for 300-fold diluted homogenate. 1% solution of $PbNO_3$ was prepared as a heavy metal salt by using distilled water.

In the *in vitro* experiment, fish preparations were divided into 4 groups according to the amount of 1% solution of $PbNO_3$ salt (0.1, 0.2 and 0.4 ml). No saline solution was applied to the diluted intestinal sections in the control group, while 0.1 ml of 1% saline solution was added to experimental 2-group, 0.2 ml to experimental 3-group, and 0.4 ml to experimental 4-group.

0.1 ml of 10-fold diluted proximal, medial and distal parts of the intestine were taken and placed in epididymis and mixed separately with 0.1 ml of 2% lactose solution as a substrate and 3 different amounts of salt (0.1, 0.2 and 0.4 ml). The same amount of 50 and 300-fold diluted intestinal parts were used as substrates with 2% sucrose and maltose solutions and 3 different amounts of salt (0.1, 0.2 and 0.4 ml, respectively). The resulting substrate mixtures were incubated for 30 minutes at $36^\circ C$. After the incubation period, 1 ml of the “Glucosa” reagent produced by the “Human” company was poured into biological preparations using a dispenser to determine the enzymatic activity of carbohydrates in each intestinal part under the influence of heavy metal salts. The reagent was incubated for 30 minutes. After the incubation was completed, the indicators were determined using the biochemical analyzer “Rayto RT 1904C Semiauto Chemistry”.

Results.

In vitro, the metabolism of lactose, sucrose, and maltose in three different parts of the intestine showed the following results under three different concentrations of 1% $PbNO_3$ salt.

Table 1.

Note: P is the confidence coefficient (*- $P < 0.05$; **- $P < 0.01$; ***- $P < 0.001$ -level of confidence compared to control).

In the control groups, lactose metabolism in the proximal part was 3.1 mmol/l, 2.15 mmol/l under the influence of 0.1 ml of heavy metal salt, 3.34 mmol/l and 0.84 mmol/l under the influence of 0.2 ml and 0.4 ml of salt, respectively. In the medial part, the indicator was 1.65 mmol/l for the control groups, and the results were 1.68 mmol/l, 2 mmol/l and 1.31 mmol/l in the remaining experimental groups. In the distal part, the control groups were 3.34 mmol/l, and 1.85 mmol/l under the influence of 0.4 ml of 1% salt (Table 1).

Under the influence of $PbNO_3$ salt, the metabolism of sucrose in the intestines showed almost no negative indicators. That is, different amounts of salt did not interfere with the breakdown of carbohydrates (Table 2).

Table 2.

Note: P is the confidence coefficient (*- $P < 0.05$; **- $P < 0.01$; ***- $P < 0.001$ -level of confidence compared to control).

Intestinal absorption of maltose also did not show negative results. It was not lower than the control group (Table 3).

Table 3.

Note: P is the confidence coefficient (*- $P < 0.05$; **- $P < 0.01$; ***- $P < 0.001$ -level of confidence compared to control).

Conclusion

According to the results obtained, *in vitro*, different amounts of heavy metal salts had a certain effect on the activity of carbohydrate-degrading enzymes in 3 parts of the intestine and the function of enterocytes on the inner surface of the intestine. When we observe the breakdown of lactose in the intestinal parts, we can see that it significantly decreased in all 3 parts of the intestine under the amount of 0.4 ml of salt. On average, no changes were observed in other amounts of salt. The effect of salt on the metabolism of sucrose and maltose was almost not noticeable. This situation can be explained by the lack of lactose-degrading enzymes in the intestines, and the sufficient presence of maltose and sucrose-degrading enzymes. In other words, the breakdown of lactose in the intestines is much lower than that of other carbohydrates, and when exposed to salt, the breakdown and absorption of lactose is even lower. Since maltose and sucrose are easily digestible carbohydrates, the effect of salt may be barely noticeable.

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